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ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Industry 5.0: making workers and civil society strong – a comprehensive approach for skill-based human centricity and stronger focus on social challenges

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Abstract. The article is based on the Bridges 5.0 project, which looks at how Industry 5.0 can be designed as a successor to Industry 4.0 by promoting aspects of human-centricity, sustainability and resilience. The project focuses on skill requirements and new approaches to skills development that bridge Industry 4.0 with Industry 5.0. Insofar as Industry 5.0 is to be understood as an “evolving concept”, it is also a process of its profiling in relation to Industry 4.0. This requires an exploration of the distinctive features of Industry 5.0. An examination of the EU’s basic 5.0-concept reveals a dual intention: Human-centricity, sustainability and resilience should be promoted within the company framework, and, at the same time, the work and production process of the companies should no longer primarily serve the interests of the shareholders but rather contribute to solving societal problems. Against this background we want to argue that the EU concept of Industry 5.0 can be understood as a multidimensional innovation ecosystem and as such can contribute to both the humanisation of working life and the democratisation of socio-ecological transformation. To this end, it is necessary, on the one hand, to consider current company-related developments (e.g. in advanced approaches in the steel sector) and, on the other hand, to examine perspectives for opening up companies to society must be examined. While the academic debate mainly focuses on the enterprise level, we want to show that the Industry 5.0 approach encourages the search for solutions to democratise the socio-ecological transformation. This requires a broadening of relevant external stakeholders – especially the civil society – that should have an impact on company decisions. Although the EU explicitly calls civil society elements to drive change, further conceptual underpinning of this ambition is still lacking. Proven and tested practicable forms of collaboration between civil society and company actors are hard to find but at least some tentative approaches (e.g., transformation councils and networks) can be outlined.

Keywords: Industry 5.0 / skills / human-centricity / steel companies / civil society

1 Introduction

The question of participation of affected stakeholders in processes of change, learning and innovation is central in social science theory and application-oriented labour research [1]. Social innovations aim to change practices of work and of designing work e.g. with regard to corporate concepts, organisational forms, management approaches, implementation of technology and technological infrastructures, and personnel development (skills). The interest of current debates is strongly focused on socio-technical perspectives addressing organisational interactions between technology and workers. Although some of those approaches are also interested in the relationship

between the company and society [2] has so far lacked an adequate conceptual design for Industry 4.0 and 5.0 with ideas for concrete negotiation processes between organisational and regional actors (including civil society).

Following the originally German concept of *Industry 4.0*, the European Union (EU) has introduced the concept of *Industry 5.0* and is thereby driving its development with a particular emphasis on the aspects human-centricity, sustainability and resilience [3]. While research papers that deal specifically with Industry 4.0 also refer to this new development [4,5], the extent to which these core aspects have not already been at the centre of Industry 4.0 is a matter of debate. This view is held, for example, by the Industry 4.0 research advisory board and platform [6]. Other critics argue similarly and are of the opinion that Industry 5.0 is a version update, which at best deserves the version number 4.1 [7].

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However, the main discussion revolves around skills issues. In [section 2](#) we want to summarize the main aspects of the skill debate (including the steel sector), knowing that it is almost impossible to draw a clear line between this and Industry 4.0 and 5.0. After summarising this debate we want to introduce a second research perspective which was also inspired by the concept of Industry 5.0, but has so far been underexposed. In [section 3.1](#) we work out impulses, argumentation and consequences according to a shift, demanded by Industry 5.0, saying that companies should expand their focus beyond maximizing profit and foster to develop solutions to major societal, in particular socio-ecological, challenges. This vision clearly goes beyond depth of transformation as well as the socially innovative dimensions of Industry 4.0 (for a discussion of the conceptual differences between Industry 4.0 and 5.0, see also [8, pp. 37-39]). As to be shown the EU's ambition requires not only greater opportunities for employees but also for regional and especially civil society actors to influence strategic corporate decisions and developments. In other words there is a need for a democratic opening up of companies for the influence of new stakeholders.

For the realignment of companies as suppliers of solutions to societal problems, the operational orientation towards relatively abstract EU targets (e.g. environmental indicators) appears necessary but insufficient to transform central strategic considerations from EU into practice [3,9]. There is a need for tools enabling permanent negotiation processes between representatives from companies and regional actors. In [section 3.2](#) we sketch approaches that are partially used in larger companies, but insufficient to implement a full scale Industry 5.0 and therefore need to be further sharpened (e.g. Corporate Social Responsibility, Shared Value). In [Section 3.3](#) we introduce instruments that are rarely used in practice, but largely in line with the intention of Industry 5.0 (e.g. Economy of Common Good, Doughnut Economy or Transfer Councils.).

In [Section 4](#), we try together the ambition of human centricity in enterprises with the ambition of a democratic opening. For this we to offer a conceptual framework of a multidimensional and civil-society-driven innovation ecosystem. In session 5 we give a short conclusion and we indicate further research needs. This requires new legislative and regulatory guidelines as well as suitable governance forms and instruments. Particularly the question of skills and skill development enabling collaboration from actors of industry and civil society marks a central challenge for future.

2 Skills in Industry 5.0

In the Industry 5.0 concept paper, the EU commission names two central problems with regard to skills in an transforming industry: Firstly, that “skills needs are evolving as fast as technologies” and that European industries cannot meet these needs; and secondly, that “young people do not feel adequately equipped with the skills needed for the future labour market” ([3], p. 18). Behind this is a content-related and a methodological

dimension: What skills should the workforce of the future have and how can companies, industries and employees detect and fulfil these skill needs more rapidly?

A large amount of literature deals with the question of which skills will be needed in the industry of the future – not just since the concept of Industry 5.0 was invented. Behrend et al. [11] deliver a comprehensive review of this literature on future skill demands alongside the categories of digital, personal, social and methodological skills. However, the specific focus Industry 5.0 puts on the relationship between technological transformation on the one and skills on the other side, distinguishing it from other strands of the debate. The central idea is that “technology serves the people, rather than the other way around” ([3], p. 15).

It is assumed that it is specifically the combination of human and technological capacities that create a new quality of opportunities for companies [12, p. 7]. A striking example of such a use of human labour would be the adoption of already existing technologies – the success of this adoption depends on an “internal investment in skills and human capital” [3]. Polakova et al. [13] also support this idea in their literature review and emphasise the role of soft skills in contributing to the ability to manage transformation processes in organisations in Industry 5.0. According to them “Human intellectual capital determines the building of dynamic capabilities that enable an organisation to adapt to radical technological changes” [13, p. 5].

Speed is perhaps the most important challenge when it comes to the question how skills should be developed in an Industry 5.0. The Skills Intelligence concept, which has been introduced by the European Commission and their agency CEDEFOP, is an approach that strives to gain an advance in the speed of skill adaptations. The idea behind this is to provide extended data on skills on a regular, timely basis to facilitate intelligent skills-related decisions (see [14]).

However, much of the data presented under the term ‘Skills Intelligence’ tends to refer to a more general European or specific sectoral level and is therefore hardly an enabler of regional decisions in companies [15, p. 13]. The focus is therefore to design the data in a way that it adequately reflects the specific circumstances of skill decisions, be it a region, a company or (regional or local) stakeholders. This specialisation is prerequisite for a profitable use of data. For example, the following questions should be considered when designing tools with an industry reference (see [15]):

- Which categories of skills should be used?
- What are the target groups?
- At which geographical levels do they operate?
- What decision do they need to make?
- What data do they need to make this decision (demand and supply information)?
- How can this data be provided (expert-driven or digital technologies driven)?

Nevertheless, some aspects that are discussed under the term Education 4.0 [16] or Education 5.0 [17] offer opportunities. Modern digital learning environments make

it not only possible to personalise learning paths and thus make learning more effective – it does this also by providing data on learning progress to learners and teachers which helps to decide what to learn next.

At the same time, skills intelligence tools do not offer a short-cut to prepare employees for organisational transformations. Instead, this rather quantitative approach does not replace the qualitative process of gaining a deep understanding of technologies and organisations. An idea to bridge the gap between new technologies and employees is therefore to address the relationship between these technologies and employees right from the beginning. If technologies are developed in co-creation processes, if employees have at least a basic level of digital skills, it is much more likely that technologies will be integrated more fluently in organisations and processes of change occur more frequently. To sum up, Industry 5.0 emphasises the relevance of humans and people. In this regard it is crucial that the people (stakeholders, workers, civil society) have the right skills for such a transformation. Empowerment, co-creation and –design are central means for a human-centric industry. To support the digital, green, and social transition of the industry the European Commission has launched the New Skills Agenda [18], Pact for Skills [19] and has or is funding more than 25 sectoral Skills Alliances [20], 14 Industrial Ecosystems [21] under the Pact for Skills are supported as well. Main results of the European Steel Skills Alliance (ESSA) [22] and the Skills Alliance for Industrial Symbiosis (SPIRE-SAIS) [23] underline the relevance of proactive skills adjustments and continuous vocational training of the existing workforce to scope the implementation of new technologies at the workplace. Beneath an upskilling of technical skills, transversal or soft skills are of increasing, indispensable and utmost importance. Additional digital and “green” skills must be complemented by an upskilling of individual/personal skills such as workplace experience, adapting change, working autonomously; methodological skills for complex problem solving, process analysis; social skills to improve communication, continuous learning, teaching and training others. First projects (e.g., IS2H4C [24], COCOP [25], ROBOHARSH [26,27]) have already implemented the integration of the social, workers perspective in a co-development and co-design of new technological developments [28].

Especially Bridges 5.0 is bridging the transformation from Industry 4.0 to Industry 5.0 by workforce and approaches like Teaching and Learning Factories. Additionally, the European Commission has launched a Community of Practice Industry 5.0 [29] which developed a Learning and Assessment Tool. The new Skills Alliance for the Green, Digital and Social Transformation of the Energy Intensive Industries (Skills4EII) under the Pact for Skills will explicitly develop skills for Industry 5.0 in the energy intensive industry (2025-2028). The energy intensive industries related skills alliances ESSA, SPIRE-SAIS, and Skills4EII underline the growing importance of online training platforms with a digital individual learning assessment, skills gap analysis and related tailor-made online training modules (steelHub [30], SKILLS4Planet [31], and the upcoming HUB5.0).

3 People over profit: suggestions from Industry 5.0 for increasing the orientation towards the common good and the role of civil society

The main mission of Industry 5.0 is to include abroad scope of perspectives and relevant actors in the ongoing transformation processes of the industry. This includes the need of an opening to new stakeholders, civil society and new approaches.

3.1 People over profit: a broader perspective and the need of democratic opening to new stakeholders

The concept of Industry 5.0 is profiled with specific reference to both the German concept of Industry 4.0 and the Japanese concept of Society 5.0 [32]. The participatory and competence-related implications of Industry 4.0 in relation to the operational level are taken up on the one hand, and the strong focus on social needs of a Society 5.0 on the other. The dominance of technology-centred strategies for action and traditional economic foundations or the prioritization of capitalist shaped target hierarchies are rejected. Industry 5.0 is particularly critical of its neoliberal character in particular and subordinates the profit demands of shareholders to the common good of citizens. The paper by Breque et al. [3] and, in particular, the related paper by the ESIR-expert-groups¹ [9] contain a number of programmatic statements that imply substantial changes in the social and economic system (see Tab. 1).

This broader understanding of the purpose of industrial production and particularly the focus on stakeholders instead of shareholders interest (*stakeholder capitalism*) leads to approaches addressing a broader range of those stakeholders in factories and beyond. As Botthof et al. [20] have worked out for German innovation policy in a way that can certainly be generalised, a variety of opening processes are taking place in education, politics, business and science in order to mobilise the diversity of knowledge sources appropriate to the complexity. What is required is a “systematic crossing of disciplinary and sectoral boundaries in the generation of knowledge and the genesis of innovations” ([33, p. 12]). Opening movements can be observed in many respects. They take place between disciplines (interdisciplinarity) and between sectors and policy fields, as well as between companies and external sources of knowledge and society (transdisciplinarity, open innovation). The new actors increasingly include “consultants and intermediaries from associations and regional/municipal institutions as well as representatives of civil society” ([33, p. 14]).

¹ ESIR (expert group on the economic and societal impact of research and innovation) is an independent high-level group of international experts that advises the European Commission on the development of a forward-looking and transformative research and innovation policy.

Table 1. Quotes from the EUs’ conceptual Industry 5.0 papers [3,9].

The existence of Industry 5.0 is closely linked to the “benefit and convenience of each citizen” [3, p. 9].
The aim is to ensure “that companies do not only act in a profit maximising way but take proper account of social/environmental/general interest concerns as part of their ‘license to operate’” [9, p. 18].

“In a globalised world, a narrow focus on profit fails to account correctly for environmental and societal costs and benefits. For industry to become the provider of true prosperity, the definition of its true purpose must include social, environmental and societal considerations. This includes responsible innovation, not only or primarily aimed at increasing cost-efficiency or maximising profit, but also at increasing prosperity for all involved: investors, workers, consumers, society, and the environment” [3, p. 13].

The ESIR-expert-group supports this approach by stating: “Industry 5.0 means first and foremost a decisive move away from neo-liberal capitalism models with a focus on production for profit and “shareholder primacy”, towards a more balanced view of value over time and a multi-valent understanding of capital – human and natural as well as financial. This change implies significantly more than due diligence for supply chains but an understanding of de-risking through resilience building. Building resilience throughout the value chain requires a people-planet-prosperity approach that focuses on short-term levers and long-term planning rather than short term profit seeking. [...] Even the increasingly popular notion of “stakeholder capitalism”, while recognising corporate responsibility for ensuring that all relevant interests represented in the firm are catered for, is insufficient to enable a full transition to Industry 5.0.” [9, p. 7].

“Industry 4.0 paradigm, as currently conceived, is not fit for purpose in a context of climate crisis and planetary emergency, nor does it address deep social tensions. On the contrary, it is structurally aligned with the optimization of business models and economic thinking that are the root causes of the threats we now face. The current digital economy is a winner-takes-all model that creates technological monopoly and giant wealth inequality. (...) Industry 5.0 actually nests the Industry 4.0 approach in a broader context, providing regenerative purpose and directionality to the technological transformation of industrial production for people-planet-prosperity rather than simply value extraction to benefit shareholders” [9, p. 5].

ESIR experts go into detail on the need to develop practices for “Governance 5.0”. According to them, it is based on “principles of co-creation and mutualism with key stakeholders starting with the most marginalised and least influential” [9, p. 20]. Elsewhere, the following statement is made: “The establishment of a culture of social dialogue at all levels (company, sector, regional and national) becomes imperative (...)” [9, p. 16].

Industry 5.0 is a value-driven initiative that attempts to shape technological change through humanistic and democratic society-related and society-driven objectives (Grand Challenges; Green Deal) [5, p. 533, 5, p. 23]. The negotiation and specification of associated normative orientations and their translation into actionable measures in the production sector requires practices for shaping learning processes and increasing the ability to reflect in complex multi-actor systems. This means a shift from solving (technical) problems by single organisations to solving societal problems by the collaboration of a multitude of actors. This could be seen as transformative innovation policy [34, p. 15, 13].”

The concept of Industry 5.0 has all aspects of a transformative innovation policy including aspects from Smart Specialization [35] and Responsible Innovation in Industry [36]. Banholzer considers Industry 5.0 as a framework of the EU strategy “to form a pan-European innovation ecosystem that is to emerge from the networking of local and regional ecosystems” [7, p. 19]. This would require a reorientation of all sectors and all actors, from the state to the private sector and civil society, and would require a new set of instruments that is more strongly based on shaping and co-shaping the market [37,17]. Adequate (regional) governance approaches are demanded. A more

recent summary of definitional characteristics from various sources was undertaken by Pollermann: “Regional governance comprises structures and processes for the deliberate regulation of collective social issues. Issues of regional development in a specific territorial area (below the nation state) are to be regarded as issues. Regional governance describes steering and regulatory structures that typically: (a) bring together state and other societal actors from business and civil society with their different logics of action and (b) include formal and informal institutions” ([38, p. 9], own translation).

Regional governance approaches were initially geared towards the collaboration of three spheres of society (state, civil society and business). More recent and more differentiated ecosystem models in the form of the quadruple or quintuple helix [39] are based on a similar constellation for such forms of collaboration. Quadruple and Quintuple Helixes are explanatory models for the emergence of innovations (see [40]). The quadruple helix approach stresses that not only politics, science and business have to interact for generating innovation. It was recognized that civil society and the media- and culture-based public also play an important role in the development of innovations and also in the production and dissemination of knowledge. The foreseeable climate change gave rise to the Quintuple Helix (fivefold innovation helix) model, which takes into account the natural environment as a fifth interacting sector.

This and how the actors from the social subsystems can collaborate in real-life experiments forms the core of social innovation processes [41]. Overall, these approaches search for the prerequisites for the mutual opening of heterogeneous actor systems and for suitable practices of common

Table 2. Opening. How, for what and by whom? Source: [42, p. 39], own translation.

ENTREPRENEURIAL	CIVIL-SOCIETY
Generate acceptance, demand, product ideas: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Management of interest groups – Proactive marketing – Crowdsourcing 	Integrate diverse experiences, perspectives and interests: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Public debate – Discourses on the future – Constructive impact assessment – Experimenting collectively (hybrid fora)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – The “implementer” has already been determined – Company, institute, authority, consortium as organiser with interests in the process 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – What, whether and by whom will be implemented is open – Needs and concerns are being explored to check whether a collective agenda can be achieved
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Instrumental opening – General framing, project orientation and decisions are made centrally, ex ante 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Democratic opening – Problematisation and action orientation – Arises decentralized in the process

problem solving, for example in enterprises. Opening processes for the mobilization of external knowledge in the context of companies have been observable since the end of the 1990s. This applies not only to consultancy services or to the incorporation of findings from application-orientated research, but increasingly also to information on needs and, above all, solutions from customers and users. In the meantime, various forms of open innovation and co-creation have developed. These include crowdsourcing and innovation competitions, hackathons, lead user methods, communities, living labs and design thinking (see [42]). However, it makes a difference whether the opening processes are driven and configured by entrepreneurial action or whether this is done by societal stakeholders. Vofß distinguishes here between instrumental (entrepreneurial) and democratic (civil society) opening [42, p. 39]).

The democratic opening up of the innovation process stands for the expansion of the spectrum of knowledge sources considered relevant in the innovation process. Companies, universities and research institutions are no longer the only relevant players in the innovation process. Citizens, customers, NGOs, social movements, etc. also play an increasingly important role as sources of articulating needs and as collaborators in developing solutions. Table 2 compares the central features of both opening processes.

Recently, there has been an increasing number of approaches in the literature that deal with the connection between innovation ecosystems and social innovations, as Terstriep et al. [43] note. The authors place the debate in the context of regional forms of governance and note that research in this area is still in its early stages [43, p. 7]. Similar to Industry 5.0, “missions or societal challenges are the focus of neighbouring approaches such as the mission-oriented or challenge-oriented regional innovation system [44,45]. Despite all the differences, what the approaches have in common is that they include (organised) civil society as an important actor alongside business, politics and science (e.g., quadruple helix).” [44,45]. One challenge here is the availability of suitable forms of governance and practices that ensure civil society participation across all phases of the innovation process. Corresponding expertise still largely needs to be built up [46].

The call for democratisation has a long tradition and goes back to Greece (Athens), the American, British and French revolutions, etc.. In particular, the debate on the democratisation of modern companies began in the 1960s and 1970s. During this time, questions of co-determination, participation and humanisation of the world of work were raised in many western industrialised countries by politicians, trade unions and labour research [47]. Industrial sociology was quick to analyse working conditions and the balance of power in companies. Experiments with workplace democracy in Sweden and Norway demonstrated alternative models of cooperative work organisation. The Hawthorne experiments (1924–1932) and the human relations movement, which addressed the social dimensions of work and their connection to job satisfaction and productivity, can be seen as the forerunners of these developments. The human relations movement contributed to employees getting more say and better working conditions [48]. Later concepts of participation, teamwork and employee-friendly corporate cultures were based on these findings. In the late 1940s and early 1950s, researchers at the Tavistock Institute of Human Relations in the UK developed a socio-technical systems approach. The approach was continuously developed internationally, but hardly found its way into operational practice. In the context of Industry 4.0 and 5.0, it is currently experiencing a renaissance [49]. Bruno Latour’s approach, in particular his actor-network theory (ANT), plays a special role in the analysis of the relationship between business and society, because it dissolves the classic distinctions between social and technical factors. Instead, Latour regards companies as networks in which people (actors) and things (non-human actors, e.g. technologies, machines, documents) jointly shape social processes [2]. However, to date there is a lack of empirical examples and of theoretical-conceptual and instrumental specifications that could help to directly link actors from companies and the region in a dialogue in co-evolutionary development processes. This is not intended to replace already institutionalised forms of negotiation, but to supplement them.

While the need for such approaches is now being articulated by many stakeholders and the demand for the involvement of civil society has almost become common

Fig. 1. Two components of Shared value according to Porter and Kramer (source: [52, p. 98]).

sense, there is still a lack of sufficiently convincing examples. “The implementation of participation often only reaches privileged population groups and individuals (...)” [47, pp. 4-5]. The difficulty of mobilising civil society and integrating it substantially into the context of the working world is particularly high. This also showed that civil society needs to be viewed in a much more nuanced way than is usually the case. A rough initial distinction can be made between non-organised civil society (citizens) and organised civil society (institutions). The extent to which citizens are actively involved depends, among other things, on their educational background, age and social class. Citizens tend to be active selectively and depending on their local or regional roots. The less they identify with a place (e.g., commuters) or are perceived to be affected by a problem, the less they are willing to get involved. Conversely, those for whom the place is the centre of their lives are more willing to get involved individually (e.g., in civic associations). Overall, activities appear to be selective and are limited in terms of time and space [50]). In contrast, representatives of organised civil society tend to operate at a regional level in a longer-term and institutionalised context, whereby an initiating role can rarely be observed empirically. This requires stimulation from corresponding funding contexts and collaborative projects in which science and universities as well as institutionalised representatives of the local and regional economy (chambers of industry and commerce) work together [50, p. 7]. Companies also tend to be among the reactive actors with a high sensitivity to time demands. Differences emerge regarding the company’s roots in the region, the degree to which the owners are connected to the region and the extent to which local managers are dependent on instructions from outside the region. The more directly affected the company is and the more opportunities it has to exert influence, the more willing it is to get involved in the community (e.g., dialogue groups, mayoral discussion groups) [50, p. 7].

Banholzer therefore considers it a precarious endeavour that Industry 5.0 was launched with a top-down impulse from the executives “without outlining a concept of the public sphere, political discourse or deliberative, agonal or pragmatist debate in pluralist democracies” [7, p. 39]. However, politics is also confronted with a general lack of such tried-and-tested concepts and corresponding experi-

ences provided by research. “Given that a large number of articles emphasise the importance of multi-level actor interaction and coordination in addressing directionality and other types of transformative challenges, it is somewhat surprising that there are so few analyses of the actual role and contribution of different actors in relation to transformative challenges” [34, p. 32].

3.2 Corporate social responsibility and social value: perspectives and limitations for a democratic opening up for civil society addressed by Industry 5.0

Following the outlined research direction, the concept of Industry 5.0 provides indications of connecting dots that can be further developed for a democratic opening up towards civil society. This includes forms of corporate governance such as corporate social responsibility and shared value (Fig. 1). Against this background, in 2021 the EU has launched an initiative to improve the EU legal framework for company law and corporate governance [9]. The aim is to orientate companies towards long-term and sustainability-oriented value creation. The initiative aims to better harmonise the interests of companies, shareholders, managers and other interest groups as well as society and support companies in anchoring socio-ecological standards in business processes and value chains [9]. According to the EU, corporate governance should relate to extensive forms of corporate social responsibility (CSR). CSR should become an effective instrument that ensures that companies not only act to maximise profit, but also fundamentally integrate social, ecological and societal goals [9]. This opens up many fields of action for companies to implement sustainability in their core business strategies:

- Supply chain responsibility: Increased responsibility for fair working conditions, wages and compliance with environmental standards along the entire supply chain; i.e., not only in the company’s own operations, but also with suppliers.
- Target-oriented CSR: Specification of targets for reducing greenhouse gas emissions, promoting renewable energies and reducing waste.
- Impact measurement: Measuring the actual impact of CSR measures using increasingly specific indicators and metrics to quantify the environmental impact.

Table 3. Common Good Matrix (source [59], own translation).

Values	Human dignity	Solidarity & Justice	Sustainability	Transparency & Participation
Actors				
A: Supplier	A1 Human dignity in the supply chain	A2 Solidarity and justice in the supply chain	A3 Ecological sustainability in the supply chain	A4 Transparency and co-decision in the supply chain
B: Owner	B1 Ethical attitude in dealing with monetary resources	B2 Social attitude in dealing with funds	B3 Socio-ecological use of financial resources	B4 Ownership and co-decision
C: Employees	C1 Human dignity in the workplace	C2 Elaboration of the employment contracts	C3 Promotion of ecological behaviour among employees	C4 Internal co-decision and transparency
D: Customer	D1 Ethical customer relationship	D2 Cooperation and solidarity to other companies	D3 Enabling ecol. use of products; recycling of waste	D4 Customer involvement; Customer driven innovation
E: Society	E1 Purpose and social impact of products and services	E2 Contribution to the community	E3 Reduction of negative ecological impacts	E4 Transparency and societal co-decision

- Sustainable finance: The greater consideration of sustainability factors in investment decisions. Socially responsible investments (SRI) and sustainable bonds (green bonds, social bonds, etc.) are examples of this.
- Transparency and reporting: Companies are required to report more transparently on their CSR activities and performance. This enables stakeholders to better understand the actual efforts and results of companies in the area of sustainability.
- Innovative technologies: Using innovative technologies such as artificial intelligence, Big Data and block chain to address sustainability issues; e.g., to improve supply chain transparency or energy efficiency.
- Social commitment: CSR not only includes environmental aspects, but also social issues such as combating poverty, promoting education and healthcare. Companies are increasingly involved in social projects and contribute to the development of their communities.
- Collaboration and partnerships: Increased cooperation between companies and governments, NGOs, academic institutions and other companies to achieve greater sustainability goals together.

However, the reference to corporate governance and CSR primarily addresses big enterprises and the main stakeholders from management, trade unions, politics and employees. Other societal actors have so far been referred

to rather incompletely and generally as “other key stakeholders” [9, p. 18], without specifying who is meant, what functions and expectations are associated with them, and without clarifying how these stakeholders should be systematically integrated into a continuous interaction process. But nevertheless Industry 5.0 moves focus from shareholder value to stakeholder value. This means the unilateral power of capital interests is fundamentally called into question.

The pressure is increased to include internal and external stakeholders who have a legitimate interest in the course or outcome of the company’s activities. This refers to concepts beyond shareholder primacy in direction of shared value approaches [51]. Although this is not new, it is also suitable for anchoring social stakeholder groups more firmly as co-designers of corporate development. Shared Value is an approach in favour of a further development in which companies could go beyond CSR and incorporate social and ecological considerations into their strategies. This approach treats social challenges as business opportunities as most effective way to achieve social progress. Shared value results from strategies and practices that contribute to a competitive advantage and at the same time strengthen the communities in which a company operates [51].

According to Porter and Kramer, companies can create shared value in three ways: by redesigning products and markets, by redefining productivity in the value chain and

by strengthening local clusters. All three options require a sufficiently robust regional market ecosystem. At the operational level, this requires a common agenda, a common measurement system, mutually reinforcing activities, constant communication and dedicated support from one or more independent organisations. Areas that are particularly well suited to the development of shared values are environmental factors, energy and water consumption, supplier involvement and dealing with employees (in terms of skills, health and safety, see [53]). Porter and Kramer's considerations are accompanied by a series of practice-orientated guidelines for implementing and measuring shared value [53].

Academics have expressed considerable doubts about the novelty, practical relevance and dissemination of the shared value approach. Although many academics agree with the ideas of Porter/Kramer to the effect that companies should actively participate in solving social problems, it is strongly questioned whether the concept presented brings anything new to international CSR research and practice [54]. For example, the integration of CSR into the core business favoured by the two authors has long been one of the challenges that have been tackled scientifically. Schormair and Gilbert [52] state that the EU Commission's CSR strategy from 2011 already goes beyond Porter/Kramer's concept. Furthermore, shared value is not the claimed reinvention of capitalism, but rather a perspective aimed exclusively at increasing long-term profitability, which hardly differs from the basic principles of conventional value creation [52, p. 103].

Despite the considerable and valid criticism of the shared value approach, it does not seem sensible to reject the approach completely. However, it would be better to remedy its weaknesses, which Schormair and Gilbert summarise as two of the most serious problems: "the one-dimensional understanding of value and the process of sharing, largely neglected by Porter and Kramer and focussed exclusively on increasing long-term profitability, which necessarily precedes the creation of so-called shared value [52, p. 104–105]. The Achilles' heel of Porter and Kramer's concept is "the creation of **shared value** without a prior **sharing of values**" [52, p. 105]. Without an explicit process of value creation between all parties involved, the self-imposed goal of bringing the economy and society closer together would be missed ([52, p. 105], own translation). Divergent value issues and the associated multiple interests and needs must be taken into account in the correspondingly necessary negotiation processes. Porter and Kramer offer no support here. The values appear to be set a priori. More far-reaching design approaches, on the other hand, would have to be based on procedures and processes of "doing shared value" or "sharing value" between stakeholders, which refers back to social innovation approaches.

Schormair and Gilbert take a similar view when they state: "In our view, the central starting point for the further development of SV [*Shared value, the authors*] is nevertheless the realisation that a forward-looking strategic CSR approach cannot be based exclusively on the profit-oriented selection of those aspects of value creation that also represent an additional social benefit from the

company's perspective. Instead, the strategic CSR approach of the future will be based on a problem-solving-centred and continuous exchange at eye level between companies and society. Strategic decisions will no longer be made solely from a monological management perspective, but will be embedded in an understanding-oriented dialogue between all affected stakeholders" ([52, p. 107], own translation). The shortcoming of previous approaches lies in the fact that the effects of entrepreneurial activities of people are excluded ([55, p. 46], own translation). There is a lack of participation and co-determination in the internal space of companies and a lack of collaboration with civil society and regional actors in the external space. The potential and scope of such concepts and instruments ultimately always revolves around the question of which internal and external stakeholders are to be specifically integrated and what influence they should have on the overall process of developing, implementing and evaluating the procedures. "This analysis necessarily begins with the question of who influences what happens in the company" ([56], own translation).

3.3 Advanced approaches for a democratic opening up for civil society beyond Industry 5.0: Economy for the Common Good, Doughnut Economy, transformation councils and networks

The following approaches are suitable for realizing the intentions of Industry 5.0 according to opening-up-process but they are not mentioned in the concept.

3.3.1 Economy for the Common Good (ECG)

One of the most far-reaching approaches to aligning companies with its social impact and involvement of societal actors is the ECG conceptualised by Felber [57]. This concept links back to concepts of "common goods" having historical roots in antiquity. In Europe in particular, the principle of the "commons", for instance jointly used areas of land, are existing for centuries. The term "common goods" gained importance in the 20th century, when the economic and political dimensions of resources and common goods were increasingly examined [58]. According to the ECG from Felber economic decisions should be evaluated according to the extent to which they promote the common good. The ECG emphasises cooperation and solidarity between companies instead of pure competition. The aim is to bring about positive change together. Values such as human dignity, justice, sustainability and democratic co-determination should be anchored in all economic activities, as should democratic forms of co-determination in companies (Tab. 3). The ECG operates with a double sufficiency perspective (resource consumption and income). In this respect, growth-critical accents are set and excessive income disparities are counteracted. A certification process (audit) is used to evaluate companies, in which authorised auditors draw up a common good balance sheet that examines suppliers, owners, employees, customers and the social environment.

The core elements of the ECG are the Common Good Report, the Common Good Balance Sheet and the Municipal Common Good Index. They are drawn up with

Fig. 2. Doughnut Economics (source [64], CC BY-SA 4.0).

the active participation of all groups involved [60]. Although ECG has only established itself in a small niche so far, it offers a convincing alternative to the shareholder principle that has been tried and tested in many companies. The interfaces with the EU's ideas on Industry 5.0 are considerable. The European Economic and Social Committee has already published their opinion according to ECG. In 2015 they made a plea for integration "into both the European and national legal frameworks" ([60, p. 18], own translation). The ECG model is therefore "close to the fundamental values of the social economy, circular economy, sharing economy, functional economy, resource-based economy and blue economy" ([60, p. 18], own translation) and could successfully contribute to the development of an ethical market economy.

While corporate governance, CSR and Shared Value are predominantly used by large companies, the ECG has so far mainly been used by small companies. The complexity and implementation of the process need to be revised accordingly. Similarly, procedures for the direct involvement could be driven forward more strongly. It is also particularly interesting that the ECG also takes regional and municipal aspects into account. For example, the focus is on the common good orientation of municipalities and communal organisations. Instruments are available with which they can subject themselves to a review of

their orientation towards the common good, whereby one criterion is the creation of sufficient incentive and reward structures for common good companies. For example, there are tried and approaches, instruments, handouts and counselling services for drawing up common good balance sheets in municipalities, communities, cities and regions, ranging from suggestions for promoting common good oriented enterprises (through lower taxes or greater consideration in the awarding of public contracts) to the introduction of local common good indices and the implementation of local economic conventions [61].

The ECG supports the democratic opening of companies to the outside world and systematically opens up opportunities for local stakeholders and civil society to exert influence. Complementary to this, municipalities and cities can now also undergo an audit or assessment of their common good orientation. Since 2014, a number of smaller cities and municipalities as well as some larger cities (e.g., Barcelona, Amsterdam, Stuttgart) have been in the process of drawing up common good balance sheets. According to experts from the Bertelsmann Foundation, more and more local authorities in Germany are orientating their sustainability management towards models of the common good and they state that the concepts of sustainability and the ECG "complement each other and can be developed and implemented in an integrated form." ([62], own translation).

3.3.2 Doughnut economy

Another concept that can help municipalities and cities to increase their focus on the common good is Raworth's concept of the Doughnut Economy [63], which is also mentioned in the Industry 5.0 concept (Fig. 2). The visualisation of her model is reminiscent of a doughnut. The outer limit of the doughnut marks the carrying capacity of nine life-sustaining systems on the planet. Exceeding this limit would lead to irreversible damage. The inner limit of the doughnut marks the limit below which a deficiency situation would arise. The Doughnut forms the possible room for mankind to manoeuvre (safe and just space). Against this background, the task of the economy is to enable people to prosper, to distribute this prosperity fairly and to regenerate the resources utilised.

While the ECG is based on expert-based evaluation procedures, the doughnut economy model is linked to dialogue-based procedures with strong involvement of civil society.

3.3.3 Transformation councils and networks

The socio-ecological transformation and the development of socio-ecologically effective practices can only succeed in complex multi-stakeholder networks, particularly with the involvement of civil society actors. For reasons of democratic legitimacy, acceptance, increasing the (social) innovation potential, effectiveness of solutions and ultimately also job quality, company-centred approaches remain undercomplex and fall short. Dörre [65] therefore calls for the expansion of co-determination in the workplace through the institutionalisation of regional climate transformation councils (consisting of trade unions, social and ecological movements) or the opening of collaboration opportunities in which democratic civil society, employees and consumers influence what and how production and distribution issues. Transformation councils represent a new approach to the regional shaping of socio-ecological transformation and the alignment of production with societal interests and demands for participation [66,67]. Established regulations and practices of industrial relations should not be relativised, but rather further developed and supplemented. The aim is to expand co-determination "particularly with regard to strategic corporate decisions" [66, p. 1]. In order to be able to shape regional structural change in a cross-sectoral and public welfare-oriented manner, "*structural policy governance is also required that can bring about the broadest possible consensus on regional development. This is where the idea of transformation councils comes in: Regional stakeholders come together in a transformation council to discuss the impact of digitalisation, globalisation and the switch to climate-neutral production on the regional economy. The key players in the respective region should be represented, who can play a decisive role in shaping local economic and labour policy and have the necessary expertise. These include employers' associations or structurally influential companies, trade unions and works councils, employment agencies, state and local government, universities and research institutions, as well as representatives of civil society*" ([66, p. 2], own translation).

In recent years, a number of differently structured and thematically focussed transformation councils and transformation platforms have emerged in Germany at federal state and municipal level, often initiated by trade unions as initiators (sometimes also under names such as transformation networks, economic councils, commissions) [66, p. 3]. Some of these experiments have also taken place on the basis of public funding. Examples include projects like CARS 2.0, MoLeWa, TRaSaar, ATLAS, ReTraSON and the Rhineland-Palatinate Transformation Agency [68]. The German Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action is now funding 27 regional transformation networks across Germany as part of the program "Transformation strategies for regions in the automotive and supplier industry" ([69], own translation).

Even though no in-depth evaluation or comparison of the projects has yet taken place, the following structural elements can be recognised according to Moch ([66], own translation): The starting point is an analyse that focuses on the cross-sector challenges in a region. This is followed by the development of action strategies and measures based on which development projects are initiated. The transformation networks are supplementing existing instruments of structural, regional and innovation policy (supplement for the state framework). The stakeholders are representatives from companies in various sectors, research institutions, labour market players, educational service providers, politicians and business organisations, social partners and civil society. They are involved in analysing problems and developing measures with a clear mandate and develop proposals for solutions that cannot be ignored by government decision-makers. Comprehensive financial resources for administrative support, an own office or functions in the network are provided for the duration of initially three years.

Further perspectives lie in the development of a transformation reporting system, building a network of transformation networks (platform; hubs) and a full-scale introduction. The qualitatively profound activation of involvement of civil society actors still seems to mark a striking gap. Regional transformation councils that are sufficiently based on civil society (as counterparts of company transformation councils) and intensively "intervene in the debates on transformation with their own proposals, demands and concepts and require their participation combined with clear rights" ([67, p. 2], own translation) are still lacking.

While the development of the skills required to realize Industry 5.0 outlined above is being driven forward intensively, particularly by European labour research, there is no comparable effort to develop skills that enable the democratic opening-up of companies and empower both employees and external stakeholders (civil society, political actors) to do so. However, there is a broad spectrum of preliminary work that could be made fruitful for such an endeavour. However, there is a broad spectrum of preliminary work that could be made fruitful for such an endeavour. For example, these are social and social-communicative skills that also become virulent in the context of participative leadership [70]. Further starting points can also be found in the debate on the management of co-evolutionary cooperation networks or transorganisational learning and develop-

Fig. 3. Industry 5.0 as a multidimensional innovation ecosystem, own depiction.

ment processes between heterogeneous partners consisting of representatives from companies, politics and science, or more generally on network management [57,71].

It is about the ability to develop effective structures that make it possible to integrate actors from very different social practice and policy fields into an efficient cooperation context and to achieve learning and development progress without having to resort to forms of hierarchical control. The challenge lies in enabling people to deal with increased forms of diversity (other interests, expectations, needs, logics of action), i.e. forms that go beyond the company's regulatory framework. Conversely, external actors should be enabled to understand and take into account the constraints and limitations of companies. This is only possible with adequate long-term dialog and adequate interaction competencies [72].

4 Framework of a multidimensional and civil-society-driven innovation ecosystem

In contrast to Industry 4.0, Industry 5.0 opens up a claim to democratisation and participation that goes beyond company boundaries and extends to questioning traditional capitalist orientations. This requires embedding and linking company design projects in specific forms of mission-orientated innovation policy and governance. Combining organizational actors with regional actors (civil society) results in the model of a multidimensional innovation ecosystem driven by civil society.

Although transformative innovation policy and its mission are also embedded in society, to the extent that they have the role of orienting and coordinating the socio-ecological transformation process, they have an impact on society and therefore form the more general framework (outer circle) in Figure 3. In any case, all fields of action (Transformative Innovation Policy, Mission, Society,

Smart Factory) should be viewed as discursively, recursively and collaboratively networked. The presentation can be developed starting with Transformative Innovation Policy (TIP) or vice versa, starting with the company. The following explanation starts with the company (smart factory), the 'heart' of Industry 5.0 and Industry 4.0.

The boundaries of the Smart Factory are open to society insofar as opportunities are sought to realise the Social Development Goals. However, little reference is made to forms of exchange with external stakeholders beyond the supply chain. Forms of open innovation (in which external sources of knowledge are incorporated according to operational calculations) are not excluded, but do not form a point of reference for Industry 4.0. In contrast, the shift from shareholder value to stakeholder value intended by Industry 5.0, combined with the demand that companies subordinate their profit interests to the interests of employees and society, requires, among other things, a significant increase in interactivity and co-evolution with regional players.

Ultimately, this is not possible in a democratic way without involving external actors from Society as stakeholders in strategic decisions. The EU concept links the legitimisation of 5.0 companies with a focus on the requirements and expectations of society. More clearly than in Industry 4.0, the coupling of enterprises and society is to be ensured not only through the operational implementation of abstract specifications and related participation offerings, but also on the basis of the active involvement of Civil Society and NGOs. However, also Industry 5.0 concept has so far largely lacked design approaches for a societal co-determination and insofar for a (civil) society driven development. As has been shown, the aim is to connect forms of corporate and regional governance and to enable co-evolutionary learning. Starting points for this kind of civil society driven development

can be found in approaches from corporate social responsibility, shared value, economy of common good or transformation councils and networks.

The Smart Factory and society are guided by the specific Mission of Industry 5.0. It is not only to become more human-centric, sustainable and resilient but also to overcome neoliberal and traditionally capitalist economic models. But in its current form, the mission remains primarily focussed on the SDG-targets. How a transformation from neoliberalism to an economy for the common good as a “societally driven social ecological transformation” can succeed remains relatively open. The necessary deliberative negotiation, implementation and coordination mechanisms and instruments have yet to be developed.

Mission-oriented transformative innovation policy or overall governance involving universities (transformation research and transformative research) can initiate the development of the necessary practices, instruments and competences (in the sense of capacity building). Based on a new innovation paradigm and, among other things, by promoting social innovations, their task would be to bring together the multitude of stakeholder groups, policy fields and spatial transformation levels (local, regional, national) in a coordinating manner, to establish infrastructures for adequate collaboration formats (e.g., labs) and to support the development of corresponding competences and skills (especially civil society and employees) [73,74].

A look at the system as a whole reveals a number of needs for further development which, although touched on in the Industry 5.0 concept, have hardly been addressed in the relevant debate on Industry 5.0 to date. In particular, the question how to strengthen societal stakeholder groups, or how to specify the role of different stakeholders and to open up opportunities for concrete deliberation and co-creation of mission, strategy and implementation measures with the participation of workers and civil society represents a critical gap for success.

5 Conclusion

The concept of Industry 5.0 opens up a space of possibility for the comprehensive humanisation and democratisation of industrial companies. Much of the current debate is concerned with exploring the organisational internal perspective (democratisation of work), to limit the power of shareholders in decision-making processes and to expand the influence of society on companies (democratisation of the economy). Against this background, research on Industry 5.0 has been focussed on aspects of the human-centred and participatory design of work and digitalisation, especially related to skills intelligence, upskilling and co-creation. In contrast, this article follows a different search direction opened up by Industry 5.0. The Industry 5.0 concept articulates very clearly that neoliberal models and premises such as the priorities of the capitalist economy need to be substantially rethought. The 5.0-concept encourages the replacement of the shareholder value principle with forms of shared value and production orientated towards the common good. Active forms of collaboration with (regional) social actors and civil society in particular should be strengthened

for this purpose. The development of suitable structures, forms of interaction, coordination and governance has only just begun. It can build on a wide range of previous work. It remains open to what extent Industry 5.0 will drive approaches towards an *Economy for the Common Good* orientation and to what extent the necessary corporate and economic democratic adjustments will be pursued and instrumentally enabled. In any case, the success of a far-reaching socio-ecological transformation depends crucially on the consolidation of deepening human-centred and participatory approaches within companies and at the same time that the principle of “turning those who are affected into participants” can be extended to civil society. To make this change and transformation happen, it is obvious or a precondition that the people (stakeholders, managers, workers, citizen representatives) have to get the right skills. The development of competencies to cope with the daily production process are just as much a part of this as the as well as the ability to engage with regional political and civil society actors in a future-oriented dialog. The integration of both perspectives into an overall picture means further developing Industry 5.0 as a multidimensional innovation ecosystem.

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Appendix

Abbreviation	Meaning
ANT	Actor-network theory
ATLAS	Automotive Transformationsplattform
Bridges 5.0	Bridging Risks to an Inclusive Digital and Green future by Enhancing workforce Skills for Industry 5.0
CARS 2.0	Cluster Automotive Region Stuttgart 2.0–Transformationsnetzwerk für den Fahrzeug- und Maschinenbau
CEDEFOP	European Centre for the Development of Professional Training
COCOP	Coordinating Optimisation of Complex Industrial Processes
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
ECG	Economy for the Common Good
ESIR	Expert group on the economic and societal impact of research and innovation
ESSA	European Steel Skills Agenda
EU	European Union
IS2H4C	Sustainable Circular Economy Transition: From Industrial Symbiosis to Hubs for Circularity
MoLeWa	Mobilität Leipzig im Wandel
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
ReTraSON	Regionales Transformationsnetzwerk SüdOstNiedersachsen
ROBOHARSH	Robotic workstation in harsh environmental conditions to improve safety in the steel industry
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
Skills4EII	Skills Alliance for the Green, Digital and Social Transformation of the Energy-intensive Industries
SPIRE-SAIS	Skills Alliance for Industrial Symbiosis (SAIS) – A Cross-sectoral Blueprint for a Sustainable Process Industry (SPIRE)
SRI	Socially responsible investing
SV	Shared value
TIP	Transformative Innovation Policy
TraSaar	TraSaar – Netzwerk für Transformation